

Novel Structure Formation During Electrolysis of Dyes

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When an alcoholic solution of an ionic dye is electrolysed in a W-tube (double bent U-tube) cell, the whole liquid gets stratified into several zones often of contrasting colours demarcated by sharp and stationary boundaries. Depending on concentration, current strength and various other factors formations such as single boundary, single band, single boundary plus a band and two bands (i.e. four sharp boundaries) appear. However, in most cases on prolonged electrolysis all such systems tend to become the double boundary formation. Such structure formation is typical of many dyes in alcohol including some acid-base indicators. There could be found no essential difference between anionic and cationic dyes. Some typical transitory behaviour has been illustrated by the case of the dye, crystal violet.

THOUGH electrolysis has in general a disrupting effect, a concomitant structure formation may also take place. This is strikingly seen¹ on electrolysing an aqueous dye solution or a coloured inorganic salt solution in a double bent U-tube (called W-tube by the author). Two sharp boundaries often appear (Fig. 1, Formation A₁) dividing the solution into three zones of sharply different pH. The neutral middle colourless zone B₁B₂ sandwiched between the two coloured zones, viz. the highly acidic zone AB₂ and the highly alkaline zone CB₁. In alcoholic solution the behaviour is generally more spectacular, as high as four or even more stationary boundaries sometimes appearing between the cathode and the anode. Some typical results with alcoholic solutions of dyes are reported in this paper.

Experimental

The experimental arrangement is as shown in Fig. 1. The cell is filled with a dye solution (2 to 20 mg/100 ml) and a D.C. voltage of about 250 volts is applied between two platinum electrodes from either a bank of lead accumulators or D.C. mains. A current of the order of one hundred microampere generally passes to start with, and it gradually decreases with time to a few tens of microamperes; meanwhile one or more sharp boundaries appear usually within the zone QRS as described below.

What happens can be best described with a typical well-known dye, say crystal violet. On applying a D.C. voltage of about 250 volts through this dye solution in alcohol a current of nearly 200 μ A passes through the solution. The later behaviour depends strongly on the dye concentration. Using a solution of concentration, 5mg/100 ml, the formation of a rather thin colourless band B₂B₃ as shown in Fig. 1 (Formation A₂) is observed within three to four hours. This band is usually sharp and either remains so or tends to get somewhat blurred with time. After

some time which may be as long as 12 hours or more another boundary at B₁ appears between two coloured solutions. (Formation B; Fig. 1), the portion B₃B₁ being somewhat less violet than the portion B₁C. If the current is allowed to continue for a day or two the whole finally takes the appearance of

Fig. 1

Double Boundary (Formation A₁), the central portion B₁B₂ being completely colourless whereas the two sides B₁C and B₂A being deep violet of almost equal intensity. With higher concentrations of dye essentially the same kind of changes takes place except that the initial appearance of the colourless band B₂B₃ (Formation A₂) is much delayed. Besides, the transition from Formation B to Formation A₁

is not so straightforward and may take place through various other kinds of band (very thin or thick) formations; these bands are usually colourless but at times they appear like thin slices of very intense colour. As crystal violet does not change colour with pH (except that its colour fades in highly alkaline solution due to carbinol base formation) no multiplicity of colour is seen in this case. With dilute solutions (say, 3mg/100ml or lower) a boundary at B_1 appears after a couple of hours or so, the column CB_1 being almost colourless (very pale brownish) and the rest deep violet. In another hour or so a colourless thin band B_2B_3 appears (Formation B), so that the colour scheme from cathode to anode becomes very pale brownish colour (CB_1), deep violet colour (B_1B_3), thin colourless band (B_3B_2) and deep violet colour (B_2A). If the current is now continued various kinds of movements and colour patterns appear; and after 24 hours or so, there develops the typical Formation B, which differs from the previous Formation B in that the colourless band B_2B_3 is much wider. However, on continuing the current, various changes take place; the cathodic zone CB_1 becomes again violet and boundaries go on appearing and reappearing. By the third day the whole thing stabilises into the normal double boundary formation (Formation A_1) typical of this system, except that there is a deeply coloured thin slice at the boundary B_1 .

Most dyes in alcohol behave more or less in this way in the sense that they pass through stages of single boundary (not shown in Fig. 1), band formation (Formation A_2) and single boundary plus band formation (Formation B) and ultimately on prolonged electrolysis assumes the double boundary formation (Formation A_1). After this (Formation A_1) is formed very little change is observed, if at all, on continuing electrolysis for weeks. It should be particularly pointed out that none of the boundaries moves with the current; they are seen to form at their particular place and remain stationary however long the current may be passed. It appears that under this condition the dye ions have stopped migrating.

We have examined nearly 200 dyes and indicators and the above is the behaviour of nearly eighty per cent of these dyes. Of course the time of appearance of different formation and phases varies from dye to dye and is also dependent upon other factors such as dye concentration, current strength, cell geometry, etc. However, one noticeable feature is that no essential difference could be found between cationic and anionic dyes. Another remarkable fact is that not only each coloured column is of uniform colour throughout but the cathode column CB_1 is not necessarily of deeper colour than the anode column AB_2 for cationic dyes. Presence of some water in the alcohol, say using rectified spirit in place of absolute alcohol, not only hastens the attainment of the final Formation A_1 (Double boundary) but many of the curious intermediate formations are skipped over. This may of course be due to the higher current strength. Some very well-known dyes which behave as above are: Methyl Violet, Alizarin, Benzopurpurin 4B, Alkali Blue 6B, Victoria Blue,

Rhodamins, Erythrosin, Amaranth, Phosphine, Taurazine, Methyl Orange, Methylene Blue, Brilliant Green, Rose Bengalee, Congo Red, Thionine, Gentian Violet, Fuchsin, Safranin, Aniline Blue, etc. In the case of some dyes the transition from Formation B to Formation A_1 is very slow requiring days, probably weeks in some cases, and so in their case, we could not wait to observe the final appearance of Formation A_1 .

Some dyes show two bands (Formation C; Fig. 1) during their transition period. Examples among common dyes are Bismarck brown, Evans blue and Calcozine blue. The bands in the case of Bismarck brown are colourless (B_2B_3) and deep brown (B_1B_4) and it takes more than 24 hr for clear formation of these bands. The later transition to the double boundary stage also takes place very slowly over a few days but the deep brown band (B_1B_4) persists. The colour scheme from anode to cathode is: Deep brown/colourless band (B_2B_3)/Very pale brown (B_3B_4)/Very deep brown band (B_4B_1)/Brown. Such multiple boundary formation particularly when the different zones are of contrasting colours presents a beautiful appearance and is suitable for lecture demonstration.

It might be pointed out that the solvent plays an important part in such structure formation during electrolysis. The behaviour in alcohol is different from that in water; most dyes show multiple boundary formation in alcohol whereas it is not so in water. However, for the same dye if boundaries form at all it is much quicker in water, which is possibly due to higher current. Besides there is a tendency of forming more boundaries in alcohol for the same dye than in water; in fact in water it is usual to have a maximum of two sharp boundaries (Formation A_1), but in alcohol as already pointed out formation of three boundaries (i.e. band plus a boundary, Formation B) is quite frequent. An additional advantage in working with alcohol is that the current strength being very small, there is no disturbing effect due to heat liberation. We have also successfully used glycol as a solvent but the necessary period of electrolysis is rather very long. We have failed in benzene, the current being too low (almost zero) in the latter case. Other conditions remaining the same a higher current strength produces boundaries quicker.

Discussion

The mechanism of such boundary formation is difficult to formulate. It is evident that taking the simple and common case of double boundary formation (Formation A_1), it is an anti-Hittorf behaviour. According to the classical Hittorf mechanism, changes in concentration should take place near the electrodes and the middle chamber should not suffer any change of concentration. This is just opposite to what is observed in our case: the middle chamber suffers practically complete depletion of ions in our W-tube. As a tentative theory we surmised that such stratifications may be due to an interaction between concentration gradient and thermal gradient both caused by electrolysis. Such interaction is known² to cause stratification. We have however given up

such an idea as the thermal effect at least in alcoholic solution is extremely low; besides no boundary formation takes place near the electrodes where such gradients are likely to occur.

Colloidal behaviour has probably hardly any part to play, because double boundary formation takes place with any electrolyte and this is easily visible with coloured electrolytes, for example potassium dichromate.^{3,4}

A way of looking at the thing (Formation A_1) is to consider the matter from the viewpoint of distribution of potential gradient. The potential gradients become low both in the cathode zone and in the anode zone with progress of electrolysis due to alkali and acid liberation. So an intermediate zone builds up where the potential gradient is high and it becomes higher and higher with progress of electrolysis. This high potential gradient in the intermediate zone drives out of it all ions and ultimately becomes colourless. In a W-tube the geometry favours the accumulation of this ion-depleted high potential zone in the central portion as this is shielded from convectional disturbance. It is however not clear why the boundary between the acid zone (or alkali zone) and the intermediate zone should be so sharp and always within the zone QRS. Neither it is clear why the dye ions almost stop migrating electrically once the boundaries are formed; in other words, the dye ions hardly get through the zone B_1B_2 even though this may be its normal migratory behaviour.

Whatever may be the cause of such boundary formation it appears that there is a hitherto unrecognised inherent tendency for each of the cathode zone and the anode zone to spread out into a zone of uniform concentration and to maintain a sharp demarcation between each other either by a single boundary or by the interposition of a column of solvent. It appears worthwhile to investigate if such a tendency may be utilised for carrying out industrial electrolysis to obtain acid and alkali without using a porous partition. As a rather wild conjecture it may also be suggested that this hitherto unrecognised structure-forming property of electric current may have played some role in the creation of life in the primordial earth.

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